

~~project~~ handbook

*Responsible Research and Innovation approach for transitioning
the traditional industry regions into digitalised industry territories.*

Grant Agreement Number: n° 873010	Acronym: DigiTeRRI
Full title: Responsible Research and Innovation approach for transitioning the traditional industry regions into digitalised industry territories.	
Project URL: www.digiterri.eu	
Project Adviser at European Commission: Cristina Marcone	
Deliverable title: Project Handbook	
Work package title: Project Management	

Delivery date: 29/02/2020	Contractual	Actual
Status: Final	Version: 002	Draft [] Final [x]
Nature	Report [x] Prototype [] Other []	
Dissemination Level	Public [x] Confidential []	

Description of the deliverable (3-5 lines)

Quick reference 'manual' for partners to consult management procedures. It will summarise the key provisions in the Consortium Agreement and the Grant Agreement in lay terms and explain the organisational structure, internal policies and procedures.

Key words

Management procedure, project structure.

DISCLAIMER

The content of the document herein is the sole responsibility of the authors and it does not necessarily represent the views expressed by the European Commission or its services.

While the information contained in the documents is believed to be accurate, the authors(s) or any other participant in the DigiTeRRI consortium make no warranty of any kind with regard to this material including, but not limited to the implied warranties of merchantability and fitness for a particular purpose.

Neither the DigiTeRRI Consortium nor any of its members, their officers, employees or agents shall be responsible or liable in negligence or otherwise howsoever in respect of any inaccuracy or omission herein. Without derogating from the generality of the foregoing neither the DigiTeRRI Consortium nor any of its members, their officers, employees or agents shall be liable for any direct or indirect or consequential loss or damage caused by or arising from any information advice or inaccuracy or omission herein.

This Handbook Is About

GENERAL INFORMATION	01
THIS HANDBOOK IS ABOUT	02
BENEFICIARIES	03
GOVERNANCE	04
GANTT CHART	08
PAYMENT PROCESS	09
DELIVERABLES	10
DELIVERABLE REVIEW PROCESS	12
MILESTONES	13
RISKS MANAGEMENT	14
SOCIAL MEDIA	16
THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	18
DOCUMENT PLATFORM	19
COMMUNICATION – E-MAIL DISTRIBUTION LISTS	20
WEBPAGE	20

Beneficiaries

No	Logo	Short name	Participant organisation name	Country	Org. Type
1		AIT	AIT Austrian Institute of Technology ¹	Austria	ROR ²
2		MUL	Montanuniversität Leoben	Austria	EDU
3		NRI	Nordlandsforskning AS	Norway	ROR
4		WeDo	WeDo Project intelligence made easy S.L.	Spain	CON (SME)
5		MAT	MATERALIA	France	Cluster ³
6		ZAT	Zentrum für angewandte Technologie Leoben	Austria	Start-up centre
7		PP	The Paper Province Ekonomisk Foerening	Sweden	Cluster
8		Värmland	Värmlands läns landsting	Sweden	GOV
9		Bruck	Standort und Marketing Bruck an der Mur	Austria	GOV
10		KAU	Karlstads Universitet	Sweden	EDU
11		GEN	Grand E-nov	France	Association
12		UL	Universite de Lorraine	France	EDU

1- Project Coordination

2- ROR = research organisation; EDU = university; CON = consultant; GOV = governmental organisation.

3- economic association

Governance

Management Structure

General Assembly (GA) involves a senior representative from each of the partners and meets face-to-face every six months. For decision purposes, each member of the GA is allocated one vote. Simple majority of the attending members is enough for decision adoption. In the event of a tied vote, the Project Coordinator (as Chair) has an additional vote.

Executive Board

The **Executive Board** (EB) is the assembly of the work packages leaders. The EB is operative body for overall coordination of the project, responsible for

- approving minor amendments to the work plan,
- requiring specific actions or reports from the project coordinator,
- reviewing the project outcomes and guarantee quality,
- holding monthly teleconferences to follow-up on the operational development,
- identifying and discussing risks and outline strategic lines and reviewing upcoming activities.

Two thirds of the EB members (or their deputies) will be required to attend to constitute a quorum with one vote for each member of the EB. Simple majority of the attending members will be enough for decision adoption. In the event of a tied vote, the Project Coordinator (as Chair) will have an additional vote.

Marianne Hörlesberger, AIT	Manfred Paier, AIT	Nhien Nguyen, NRI	Brigitte Kriszt, MUL	Eamonn McCallion, KAU	Angel Honrado, WeDo	Marianne Hörlesberger; AIT
WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7
Project Management	Stocktaking / Mapping	Visioning	Working out the Roadmaps	Implementation and Improvement	Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation	Ethic Requirements

Coordinators in the Territories

Coordinators in the three territories

The coordinators in the territory support the communication. Data scope and collection, specifics of the region, contacts to stakeholders, implementing actions, policy instruments. ...

The coordinators of the three territories are:

- For **Värmland**, Sweden: Eamonn McCallion, KAU
- For **Grand Est**, France: Jean-Jacques Bernardini, GEN
- For **Styria**, Austria: Brigitte Kriszt, MUL

External Advisory Board

NAME	POSITION & ORGANIZATION	CONTRIBUTION
Morten Øien	Relations Manager at Zacco Norway AS	Handling of international contracts and advice on innovation & IPR as main areas of responsibility.
Reine Lundin	Head of Digitalization Uddeholm	Digitalisation within traditional industries
Andreas Kassler	Prof Computer Science, Karlstad University	Collaborative research Academy & Business
Iris Filzwieser	Chief Financial Officer (CFO) of Mettop	Innovative system solutions in metallurgy
NN		Representative from government and / or NGO representing citizens will be identified and reported to the project officer till the third project months

The External Advisory Board meets once per year, being reimbursed for their travel and subsistence expenses using funds reserved specifically for this purpose.

Gantt Chart

DigiTeRRI Payment Process

1	The whole project volume	2.004.037,50	100%
2	Pre-financing	1.603.230,00	80%
3	Guarantee Fund (EC)	100.201,88	5%
4	Pre-financing minus Garantie Fund	1.503.028,12	
5	Redistribution of pre-financing at project start due to Consortium Agreement	601.211,25	40%
6	Redistribution of pre-financing after project month 12 according to the Consortium Agreement	901.816,87	60%
7	Difference "whole project volume" - "pre-financing"	400.807,50	
8	Interim payment by EC (50% of line 7)	200.403,75	
9	Garantee Fund (EC)	100.201,88	
10	Distributed at the end of the project	300.605,63	

European Commission

	No	Deliverable name	WP		Type ⁴	DL ⁵	Date ⁶
D22	D7.1	H - Requirement No. 1	WP7	AIT	Ethics	CO	M 01
D23	D7.2	POPD - Requirement No. 2	WP7	AIT	Ethics	CO	M 01
D24	D7.3	H - POPD - Requirement No. 4	WP7	AIT	Ethics	CO	M 01
D01	D1.1	Project handbook	WP1	AIT	R	PU	M 02
D04	D2.1	Frame for the mapping	WP2	KAU	R	PU	M 03
D19	D6.1	Project website	WP6	WeDO	Dec	PU	M 03
D08	D3.1	List of identified stakeholders with identification process	WP3	MUL	R	CO	M 04
D05	D2.2	Data collection report	WP2	AIT	R	CO	M 05
D20	D6.2	Plan for the dissemination and exploitation of results v1	WP6	WeDO	R	CO	M 05
D02	D1.2	Initial Data Management Plan	WP1	AIT	ORDP	CO	M 06
D06	D2.3	Description of the R&I ecosystem landscapes of each the three territories	WP2	AIT	R	PU	M 07
D07	D2.4	Regional-specific transition practices	WP2	UL	R	PU	M 09
D09	D3.2	Framework for RRI implementation in R&I ecosystems of the three territories	WP3	NRI	R	PU	M 11

4- Nature of report: R = report, Dec = Webpage, ORDP=Open Research Data Pilot, Ethics

5- DL = dissemination level

6- Delivery date in project month

	No	Deliverable name	WP		Type ⁴	DL ⁵	Date ⁶
D10	D3.3	Report on a vision for each territory for resilient the R&I ecosystems by RRI approach in the transition to digitalisation	WP3	AIT	R	CO	M 12
D11	D4.1	Roadmap workshop design	WP4	MUL	R	CO	M 12
D25	D1.4	Policy brief of the first reporting period	WP1	AIT	R	PU	M 15
D12	D4.2	Report on the three built roadmaps	WP4	AIT	R	CO	M 18
D13	D4.3	Collection of the individual action plans of three territories	WP4	MUL	R	CO	M 22
D14	D4.4	Decision on interpretation of the results of the roadmap and typology of the regions	WP4	NRI	R	CO	M 25
D15	D5.1	Report on the first implementation of roadmaps actions with respect to territorial change and RRI approach	WP5	PP	R	CO	M 26
D16	D5.2	Report on the changes detected by the monitoring	WP5	AIT	R	PU	M 32
D17	D5.3	Evaluated framework and measures	WP5	KAU	R	CO	M 34
D03	D1.3	Final Data Management Plan	WP1	AIT	ORDP	CO	M 36
D18	D5.4	White book (lessons learnt)	WP5	MUL	R	PU	M 36
D21	D6.3	Plan for the dissemination and exploitation of results v2	WP6	WeDO	R	CO	M 36
D26	D1.5	Policy brief of the second reporting period	WP1	AIT	R	PU	M 36

Deliverable Review Process

1. **Outline** (content and scope) of deliverable sent to the coordinator – **1 month before the deadline.**
2. **Full version** of deliverable sent to the coordinator – **14 days before the deadline.**
3. **Two reviewers** (EB members, however, familiar with the topic but not the author) have a critical view for not more than **5 days.**
4. **Final version of deliverable** sent to the coordinator – **2 days before the deadline.**

Each milestone is linked to a deliverable thus the defined milestones are reached by the submission of the respective deliverable.

No	Milestone Name	WP involved	Estimated Date	Means of Verification	Lead
M1	Data management and ethical issues	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4	Month 6	Deliverable 1.2. Data Management Plan	AIT
M2	Maps about the R&I ecosystems in the three territories	WP2	Month 7	Deliverable 2.3. Description of the R&I ecosystem landscape of each of the 3 territories	AIT
M3	Regional-specific transition practices	WP2	Month 9	Deliverable 2.4 with a common list of practices and specificity of each territory	UL
M4	List of stakeholders	WP3, WP4, WP5	Month 4	Deliverable 3.1 identified stakeholder with organisation, type of organisation, contact	MUL
M5	Designed roadmap procedure	WP4	Month 12	Deliverable 4.1 precisely planned workshops with agenda and methods how to work together, date, location also in the languages of each territory	MUL
M6	Decision on interpretation of the roadmap results and typology of the regions	WP4	Month 25	Deliverable 4.4. Report on the interpretation of the results of the roadmap and typology of the regions, a study on diversity of territory and action or general guidelines on actions for territories in transition state	NRI
M7	Implementation of actions	WP5	Month 26	Deliverable 5.1 Report on the first implementation of roadmaps actions with respect to territorial change and RRI approach	PP
M8	Monitoring of the changes	WP5	Month 32	Deliverable 5.2 Report on the changes detected by the monitoring	AIT
M9	Final strategy for disseminating and using the project results completed	WP6	Month 36	Plan for the dissemination and exploitation of results (D6.3) submitted and approved	WeDo

DigiTeRRI Risks Management

A continuous risk identification, evaluation and monitoring activity is included in WP1 to provide the necessary tools for timely detection and control of any significant risks (both threats and opportunities). Some risks, however, are unavoidable and can already be identified in relation to the proposed work. Risk management in DigiTeRRI is conceived as a 'bottom-up' activity that will span from intra-WP work to strategic interfacing between different WPs, to risks raised through consultations with the EAB and the stakeholders at large. The task will also include definition of appropriate mitigation (i.e. actions to influence the probability and/or impact of each risk before it happens) and contingency (i.e. actions to take once the risk happens) plans, which will be periodically reported to the Commission.

No	Description of risk	WPs involved	Proposed risk-mitigation measures	Severity ⁷
R1	Target groups of stakeholders representing the quadruple helix are not willing or have no resources in taking part in the roadmap process.	WP3, WP4, WP5	Frequently communication with the person in charge of the territory. For each territory a person in charge for coordinating the work in the territory is appointed in the negotiation phase of the project. The task leader of Task 3.1 together with the WP3 leader support the territories for addressing and attracting stakeholders.	medium
R2	Stakeholders do not understand the complex approach of RRI.	WP3, WP4, WP5	Knowledge transfer of other RRI projects in which DigiTeRRI partners are involved. Transfer of best practice from the running H2020 projects I AM RRI and SeeRRI, and others. Break down RRI approach to clear messages with respect to regions (MoRRI). Continuous knowledge exchange with European RRI experts on ongoing research (e.g. studies, conferences, expert panels).	medium
R3	Actions performed in the implementation phase do not cause significant change in data (mapping of R&I ecosystem)	WP3, WP4, WP5	Be attentive to the means implemented and collaborations developed in each region to support companies in the digital transition - be sure to develop a model that can be common to all regions.	low
R4	Digitalisation in industry is even faster process than project roadmap process	WP3, WP4, WP5	Digitalisation only on business and technology and not on RRI. Roadmap can be more devoted to RRI. Adaption of roadmap process to the need of the territories, see workplan.	low
R5	Stakeholders do not understand the complex approach of RRI.	WP5	Evaluation of all action events in the implementation phase will demonstrate the change process anyway.	low
R6	Big difference in socio-culture, status of digitalisation degree, development strategies of territories lead to not comparable results.	WP5	Each project partner has the obligation to take part in a monitoring function in the roadmap processes of the other territories; so, transfer of experience to the own region is given. In the implementation phase a share point on best practises is implemented in Task 5.4.	medium
R7	Dissemination via social media does not reach the target group of the socio-culture	WP6	PR events in the territories.	low

⁷- Level of likelihood: Low/Medium/High

No	Description of risk	WPs involved	Proposed risk-mitigation measures	Severity ⁷
R8	Implementation of actions in relatively short time.	WP5	<p>Commencement of the implementation: Generally, the implementation starts with the beginning of the project. The stakeholders are engaged starting with the first workshop, which can be already considered as an implementation. The mapping, the development of the framework, and working out of the roadmap actions with stakeholders have to be developed before the specific implementation phase, where concrete actions are implemented. Since the people affected by the actions for implementation already participate in the workshops for developing the vision, framework, and the roadmap itself starting in month 10. The implementation of the co-created action (done with the stakeholders in each territory), can start in month 23 (all other actions, such as vision and roadmap are developed together with the stakeholders during the project). The interaction with the three territories is furthermore supported by a coordinator in each territory (see 3.3.5). In addition, the whole project is designed as a roadmap, therefore all tasks of a roadmap development ensure a successful way to the implementation. In addition, the task load for AIT, MUL, NRI is linked in a way so that the support in the specific work packages is ensured. The collaboration in the ongoing projects I AM RRI and SeeRRI demonstrate a constructive work.</p>	medium

WeDo feeds these channels based on the weekly plan.

<https://twitter.com/digiTeRRI>

...

<https://twitter.com/digiTeRRI>

How are we going to find our stakeholders?

1 month - 6 months

example one quarter:

	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday
twitter	#R&lecosystem	#R&lecosystem	#scientificimpacts	#R&lecosystem	#citizenscience
linkedin	#R&lecosystem			#scientificimpacts	
youtube		#scientificimpacts		#scientificimpacts	

Note: Red arrows point from Tuesday's #R&lecosystem to Wednesday's #scientificimpacts and Thursday's #scientificimpacts. Blue arrows point from Tuesday's #scientificimpacts to Wednesday's #scientificimpacts and Thursday's #scientificimpacts to Friday's #citizenscience.

social networks

follow us

#H2020
#DigiTERRI
#OpenAccess
#Researchers
#CitizenScience
#PublicSector
#ethics
#RRI
#Swafs

#digitalization
#industrialdigitalization
#territorialinnovation
#smartindustry
#ris3
#SDGs

The European Commission acknowledgement

Any dissemination activity related to DigiTeRRI must include the following sentence acknowledging the European Commission funding. Only activities including the EC logo (European Union emblem), except in the case of scientific publications, and the acknowledgement can be reported as part of DigiTeRRI dissemination work.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement n° 873010.

Document Platform

SharePoint will finally serve as platform for sharing, processing, and editing data and documents. SharePoint is a web-based collaborative platform that integrates with Microsoft Office. AIT hosts the SharePoint server. It is password protected.

<https://portal.ait.ac.at/sites/DigiTeRRI/>

The screenshot shows a SharePoint site for 'DigiTeRRI'. The interface includes a top navigation bar with 'BROWSE' and 'PAGE' options. Below this is a header section with the 'DigiTeRRI' logo and an 'EDIT LINKS' button. A left-hand navigation pane lists 'Home', 'Documents', 'Recent', 'custom list', 'Test', and 'Site Contents', with an 'EDIT LINKS' button at the bottom. The main content area features a 'Get started with your site' section with four tiles: 'Share your site.', 'Add lists, libraries, and other apps.', 'What's your style?', and 'Your site. Your brand.'. Below this is a 'Documents' section with a '+ new document or drag files here' prompt and a table of existing documents.

✓	📄	Name	Modified	Modified By
		(1) Important Documents	... 13 minutes ago	☐ Marianne.Hoerlesberger@ait.ac.at
		(2) Meetings	... 12 minutes ago	☐ Marianne.Hoerlesberger@ait.ac.at
		(3) Workpackages	... 12 minutes ago	☐ Marianne.Hoerlesberger@ait.ac.at
		Test	... 2 hours ago	☐ Marianne.Hoerlesberger@ait.ac.at

Communication – E-mail Distribution Lists

Who is in the list	List name	What does this mean
All partners	all@digiterri.eu	All members of the DigiTeRRI team
General Assembly	ga@digiterri.eu	A senior representative from each of the partners
Executive Board	eb@digiterri.eu	Each WP leader
Territorial coordinator	territories@digiterri.eu	Each territory is co-ordinated by a person in charge

WEBPAGE

www.digiterri.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement n° 873010.